

Rationality and experientiality in product design

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Abstract Several studies on decision making allow us to observe that specialists use one of two systems to define their projects: rational (i.e., inferential or analytical system that operates by rules of reasoning, relatively affect-free) or experiential/intuitive (i.e., learning or automatic system that is intimately associated with affect). This paper presents a study that aimed to evaluate the reasoning process when making decisions of product designers in comparison to other professionals that work in the same field (i.e., Engineers and Architects). For this purpose, we used the Rational-Experiential Inventory (REI). Overall, our results show a significant difference between the engineers and the other professionals: they make decisions based on a more rational and less experiential system than architects and designers.

Keywords *Design decision making, Design intuition, Product design, Rational-Experiential Inventory*

Introduction

When confronted with several options, designers go through a cognitive process defined as judgment that makes it possible for them to make a choice between alternatives (Simon, 1996/1969). Several studies (e.g., Epstein, 1994) on judgment and decision making allow us to observe that people use one of two systems (dual-process theories) to define their projects: rational (i.e., inferential or analytical system that operates by rules of reasoning, relatively affect-free) or experiential/intuitive (i.e., learning or automatic system that is intimately associated with affect). Getting to know the process of how product designers make decisions is a way of understanding how their mental process works by learning if they rely more on their past experiences (experiential/intuitive system) or in their ability to reason about the subject (rational system) to make a choice while in a new project.

Assuming that the experiential/intuitive system is based on the person's experience and personality, professionals with different academic backgrounds may have unique profiles in the judgment and decision making process. Therefore, our goal is to look at the way professionals deal with their alternatives, trying to map their patterns of decision making. Designers, Engineers, and Architects, for example, develop projects that imply on making high impact decisions, and studies that try to compare how these individuals make decisions are not yet fully described.

Our hypothesis is that designers make decisions in a different way than other professionals. Design is known by its particular "design culture", which is commonly related to creativity and innovation. Therefore, designers may need to think in a more intuitive way than other professionals from areas in which structured problems that require solely reasoning are the most common issues in everyday practice. The goal of this research is to evaluate designers intuitive decision making process, in comparison to other professionals that work in

projects related to new products. For this purpose, we carried out a survey using the Rational-Experiential Inventory, described in the following section.

Methods

The research method consisted in an online survey. The instrument included questions related to the participants' demographic characteristics and the Rational-Experiential Inventory—REI (Pacini and Epstein, 1999). REI consisted of two main scales: Rationality ($\alpha = .85$), which corresponded to rational and analytical thinking style (e.g., "I am not a very analytical thinker") and Experientiality ($\alpha = .89$), which corresponded to intuitive and affective thinking style (e.g., "I believe in trusting my hunches"). Each scale included subscales of self-reported ability and engagement. Measures of ability refer to reports of high level of ability to either think logically and analytically (Rational Ability; $\alpha = .83$) or to rely on one's intuitive impressions and feelings (Experiential Ability; $\alpha = .80$). Measures of engagement refer to reliance on thinking in a logical/analytical manner (Rational Engagement; $\alpha = .67$) or on feelings (Experiential Engagement; $\alpha = .85$) when making decisions. Each scale is composed of 20 items (10 for ability and 10 for engagement) that are evaluated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (definitely not true of myself) to 5 (definitely true of myself).

This was a descriptive, cross-sectional study with a convenience and snowball sampling. The sample was accessed through the researchers' networking and their peers. The only criterion for exclusion of the study was not being graduated in one of these pre-established areas or ever worked in the creation of new products.

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, Version 21.0. To test the differences between thinking styles, we conducted paired t-tests. To test differences between professional background (Designers x Engineers and Architects), we conducted

Univariate Analysis of Variance (ANOVAs). The dependent variable was the REI scales and subscales. Note that results were consistent even when age or gender was included as covariates in the ANOVAs, therefore, we'll only report main effects.

Results

Our sample consisted of 20 Designers, 30 Engineers, and 20 Architects. Overall, 64.3% of subjects were male. The mean age of subjects was 36.9 years ($SD = 12.0$). The average age for the Designers was 29.7 years ($SD = 3.8$), 41.2 years ($SD = 13.4$) for Engineers, and 37.7 years ($SD = 12.2$) for the Architects.

Overall results indicate that Designers and Engineers tend to rely more on Rational thinking ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.45$, and $M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.39$, respectively) than Experiential thinking ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.50$, and $M = 3.04$, $SD = 0.67$, respectively), $t(19) = 3.60$, $p = 0.002$, and $t(29) = 8.48$, $p < .001$, respectively.

In addition, Engineers showed a tendency to rely more on rational thinking style compared to Architects ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.60$), $F(2, 67) = 2.64$, $p = .079$, $MSE = 0.60$, $\eta^2_p = .073$ for the Rationality scale. This effect seems to be a result of their reliance on their ability to think logically (Rational Ability subscale), because Engineers ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.46$) had higher scores compared to Architects ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.71$), $F(2, 67) = 3.72$, $p = .029$, $MSE = 1.13$, $\eta^2_p = .10$.

Regarding Experientiality thinking style, our results show exactly the opposite, with Architects showing higher reliance on Experiential thinking style ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 0.46$) compared to Engineers; Designers showed a tendency to rely more on Experiential thinking ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.64$), $F(2, 67) = 10.01$, $p < .001$, $MSE = 3.28$, $\eta^2_p = .23$. This effect of greater reliance on Experiential thinking for Architects seems to be a result of both Experiential Ability and Engagement ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 0.48$, and $M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.58$, respectively) compared to Engineers ($M = 3.24$, $SD = 0.70$, and $M = 2.83$, $SD = 0.74$, respectively), $F(2, 67) = 5.64$, $p = .005$, $MSE = 1.91$, $\eta^2_p = .14$, and $F(2, 67) = 12.82$, $p < .001$, $MSE = 5.73$, $\eta^2_p = .28$, respectively. Designers reliance on Experiential thinking was significantly lower than Architects for Experiential Ability ($M = 3.34$, $SD = 0.45$) and higher than Engineers for Experiential Engagement ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 0.63$).

Conclusions

The goal of this research was to evaluate the process involved in judgment and decision making when developing a project in product design. Therefore we have compared thinking styles when designing a product from Designers, Engineers, and Architects who work in projects related to new products. Our findings suggested that all professionals make decisions using both rational and experiential systems, even though some (Designers and Engineers) might favor one process (Rational) over another (Experiential) as can be observed from paired comparisons.

A comparison between professions showed a cross-comparison for Architects, who favor Experientiality, and Engineers, who favor Rationality. Although Designers did not show a significant difference compared to Engineers and Architects, their scores on the Rationality scale and its subscales were somehow in between those of Architects and Engineers, suggesting they might be more likely to find a balance on their reliance on different thinking styles. That is, Designers showed that, when comes to judging options and making decisions, they rely on their analytical thoughts, but also use their past experiences and intuition.

This account suggests that people who can and do rely on rational thinking might also have irrational thoughts or perhaps are conflicted about what is rational and what is the value of experience. The way that each professional category processes information, evaluate available data and make decisions can be determinant in the way that the project and the product will be developed. For these reasons it is crucial to identify which decision-making systems are used while developing a new product.

Results of the current study should be considered in the context of certain methodological limitations. Firstly, this study used a cross-section design and should be considered exploratory. Secondly, our small sample size precludes other refinement processes such as more robust statistical analysis. Thirdly, these results are limited to this sample and should not be generalized. In spite of these limitations, the present study contributes in a significant way to the knowledge surrounding the relevance of evaluating the decision making processes. Fourthly, as with all voluntary surveys, there is the risk of self-selection bias. All the participants of our sample are Brazilians, which means that they have a similar demographic profile.

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations of the Rational-Experiential Inventory (REI) Scales and Subscales.

Variable	Total Sample M(SD)	Designers M(SD)	Architects M(SD)	Engineers M(SD)	p
Rational	4.1(0.4)	4.0(0.4)	3.9(0.6)	4.2(0.3)	0.07
Engagement	4.1(0.4)	4.1(0.5)	3.9(0.5)	4.1(0.4)	0.27
Ability	4.1(0.5)	4.0(0.5)	3.9(0.7)	4.3(0.4)	0.04
Experiential	3.3(0.6)	3.4(0.4)	3.7(0.4)	3.0(0.6)	0.00
Engagement	3.2(0.7)	3.5(0.6)	3.7(0.5)	2.8(0.7)	0.00
Ability	3.4(0.6)	3.3(0.4)	3.7(0.4)	3.2(0.7)	0.00

The highlight of our study is that our online search of the literature didn't find other studies reporting REI-40 being used while comparing architects, engineers and designers, what prevents us of comparing our findings. The way that professionals make decisions warrants further investigation. Furthermore, it is important to understand if they would have better results when developing a new product if architects, engineers or designers used more of their rational or experiential system. Also, the understanding of the relation between the REI scales and emotionality could benefit from further investigation.

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